

Annex B – Search Strategy Summary for the Scoping Review

Period search was conducted	15 July 2021 to 31 August 2021
Inclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health Service User • Psychiatric patients • Chronic mental illness • Vocational rehabilitation • Psychosocial rehabilitation • Occupational therapy • Low-income, low-middle- income and upper-middle-income countries • English language • Published from 2011 and later
Exclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic and scoping reviews • Source published in other languages, not English. • Sources published prior to 2011. • Sources from high-income countries • Full-text not available
Libraries	Worldwide
Pubmed, Medline, CINAHL, PsycInfo, Science Direct,	"Mental disorders"[MESH] AND (Severe OR Chronic OR long-term OR persistent) AND ("Psychiatric Rehabilitation"[Mesh]) OR "Rehabilitation, Vocational"[Mesh] OR "work rehabilitation" OR "Occupational Therapy"[MESH])
Google Scholar, HINARI and Wiley online	("Vocational Rehab"* OR "Work Rehab*") AND ("Severe mental illness" OR "Chronic Mental illness") AND "Occupational Therapy" NOT ("North America" or Europe*)
EBSCOhost, Cochrane library, Scopus,	(("Psychiatric Rehabilitation" OR "Rehabilitation, Vocational" OR "work rehabilitation" OR "Occupational Therapy") AND (mental disorders OR mental illness OR psychiatric disorders OR psychiatric illness) NOT (("North America" OR Europe*)) AND ((severe OR chronic OR long-term OR persistent)).
Grey Literature Sources	https://libguides.sun.ac.za/medicine/e-theses https://wiki.lib.sun.ac.za/index.php/SUNScholar/Completed_theses_and_dissertations